

ISic1256

I.Sicily inscription 1256

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

Seen by Campagna 2005-03-30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. θεαῖς
2. ἀγναῖς
3. χαριστή
4. ριον
5. Λ(ούκιος) · Μάλιος
6. Ἑρμῆς
7. ῥέκτας

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492862

EDCS 39101624

PHI 140744

Bibliography

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Photo L. Campagna 2005-03-31